

Women-Specific Fashion and Apparel MSMEs and the Socio-Economic Well-Being of Women in North Central Nigeria

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Abstract

Fashion and apparel (MSMEs) have increasingly been recognised globally as a catalyst for economic growth and development. In recent years, there has been a growing scholarly interest in understanding how women-specific enterprises contribute to improving the socio-economic well-being of women, which has been neglected over the years. This study examined and analysed the role of women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs in promoting the socio-economic well-being of women in North Central Nigeria. The paper specifically identifies the various types of women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs in North Central Nigeria. The paper also suggests the various strategies that can enhance the socio-economic well-being of women engaged in fashion and apparel MSMEs in North Central Nigeria. A thematic literature review was carried out, and the empowerment and intersectional theories were used as a framework for the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design coupled with cluster and purposive sampling techniques. Data collection encompassed quantitative techniques, which were facilitated through structured questionnaires, and qualitative methods, incorporating focus group discussions and key informant interviews. The study population included all adult women residing in the three selected states of North Central Nigeria. Taro's formula was used to select 1,111 respondents. The population was clustered into the states of the zone, the senatorial districts, and the local government areas. A proportionate sampling procedure was applied to determine an appropriate sample that represented each cluster. The analysis of data was done at the univariate level (frequency tables, mean, and standard deviation) and the multivariate level (linear regression models). Findings indicated that 69.9% of respondents owned MSMEs, and more than 50% of respondents agreed that fashion and apparel MSMEs enhanced their socio-economic wellbeing in different dimensions. The hypothesis was significant at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that all women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs contributed positive socio-economic outcomes, and the qualitative data corroborated these findings. The study recommended the encouragement of women to participate in fashion and apparel MSMEs, and the government should continue to support women who are engaged in fashion and apparel MSMEs through loans and grants to enhance their growth and development.

Keywords: Fashion, Apparel, Socio-economic, Well-being, Women, North Central Nigeria.

Kuzey Orta Nijerya'da Kadınlara Özel Moda ve Giyim KOBİ'leri ve Kadınların Sosyo-Ekonomik Refahı

Özet

Moda ve giyim sektöründeki KOBİ'ler (küçük ve orta ölçekli işletmeler), küresel ölçekte ekonomik büyüme ve kalkınmanın katalizörü olarak giderek daha fazla kabul görmektedir. Son yıllarda, kadınlara özel işletmelerin kadınların sosyo-ekonomik refahını iyileştirmeye nasıl katkıda bulunduğunu anlamaya yönelik artan bir akademik ilgi söz konusudur; bu konu yıllarca ihmal edilmiştir. Bu çalışma, Kuzey Orta Nijerya'daki kadınlara özel moda ve giyim KOBİ'lerinin kadınların sosyo-ekonomik refahını artırmadaki rolünü incelemiş ve analiz etmiştir. Makale, özellikle Kuzey Orta Nijerya'daki kadınlara özel moda ve giyim KOBİ'lerinin çeşitli türlerini tanımlamaktadır. Makale ayrıca, Kuzey Orta Nijerya'daki moda ve giyim KOBİ'lerinde çalışan kadınların sosyo-ekonomik refahını artıracak çeşitli stratejiler önermektedir. Tematik bir literatür taraması yapılmış ve çalışma için güçlendirme ve kesişimsellik teorileri çerçeve olarak kullanılmıştır. Çalışma, küme ve amaçlı örnekleme teknikleriyle birlikte tanımlayıcı bir anket araştırma tasarımını benimsemiştir. Veri toplama, yapılandırılmış anketler aracılığıyla kolaylaştırılan nicel teknikleri ve odak grup görüşmeleri ve kilit bilgi verenlerle yapılan görüşmeleri içeren nitel yöntemleri kapsamıştır. Çalışma popülasyonu, Kuzey Orta Nijerya'nın seçilen üç eyaletinde ikamet eden tüm yetişkin kadınları içermektedir. 1.111 katılımcı seçmek için Taro formülü kullanılmıştır. Popülasyon, bölgenin eyaletlerine, senatörlük bölgelerine ve yerel yönetim bölgelerine göre kümelendirilmiştir. Her kümeyi temsil eden uygun bir örneklem belirlemek için orantılı örnekleme yöntemi uygulanmıştır. Veri analizi tek değişkenli düzeyde (frekans tabloları, ortalama ve standart sapma) ve çok değişkenli düzeyde (lineer regresyon modelleri) yapılmıştır. Bulgular, katılımcıların %69,9'unun KOBİ sahibi olduğunu ve katılımcıların %50'sinden fazlasının moda ve giyim KOBİ'lerinin sosyo-ekonomik refahlarını farklı boyutlarda artırdığı konusunda hemfikir olduğunu göstermiştir. Hipotez, %0,05 anlamlılık düzeyinde anlamlı bulunmuş olup, tüm kadınlara özel moda ve giyim KOBİ'lerinin olumlu sosyo-ekonomik sonuçlara katkıda

bulduğunu ve nitel verilerin bu bulguları doğruladığını göstermiştir. Çalışmada, kadınların moda ve giyim sektöründeki KOBİ'lere katılımının teşvik edilmesi ve hükümetin, bu sektörlerde faaliyet gösteren kadınların büyüme ve gelişmelerini desteklemek amacıyla kredi ve hibeler yoluyla desteğini sürdürmesi önerilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Moda, Giyim, Sosyoekonomi, Refah, Kadınlar, Kuzey Orta Nijerya.

INTRODUCTION

Women's economic participation is increasingly recognised globally as a catalyst for economic growth, development and poverty alleviation. Women entrepreneurs contribute significantly to economic growth by creating new commercial activities, generating jobs, and producing goods and services for society (Abdulraheem et al., 2024). In developing economies, micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) serve as the lifeblood of the economic structure. In Nigeria specifically, MSMEs constitute 96.9% of all businesses, contribute 46.3% to the GDP, and employ nearly 88% of the national labour force (Abdulmumin, 2025). Within this vibrant ecosystem, women play a pivotal role, accounting for 41% of micro-business ownership in Nigeria, with approximately 23 million female entrepreneurs operating in this segment.

The fashion and apparel industry represents a distinctively gendered sector within the MSME landscape. Women are frequently drawn to businesses that are culturally acceptable and compatible with their communities, such as fashion design, weaving, embroidery, and simple textile ventures. This sector allows women to navigate the informal economy, often starting with minimal capital while leveraging indigenous skills to secure livelihoods for their households. The fashion and apparel value chain is multifaceted, encompassing raw material sourcing (such as cotton production), spinning, weaving, dyeing, designing, garment production, and retailing (Moungar, 2018).

Fashion and apparel MSMEs offer immense potential for value-added benefits; it is estimated that up to 600% of value can be created along the cotton value chain. For women, this sector is not merely about clothing production; it is a critical source of economic empowerment and cultural preservation. In regions like North Central Nigeria, the value chain includes ancient artisanal traditions, such as the hand-woven fabrics of the Ebira and Tiv people, alongside modern fashion design and retail. This sector matters profoundly for women's livelihoods because it provides a "second chance" at economic integration for marginalised groups and offers a pathway from subsistence living to active economic engagement. Furthermore, income generated by women in these value chains is often reinvested directly into household welfare, specifically in food, clothing, and children's education, thereby stabilising the rural and peri-urban economy.

North Central Nigeria comprises states such as Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger, Plateau, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), which together present a unique economic and cultural landscape for this study. This region is strategically significant as the "Central Zone" for cotton production, often referred to as "white gold", which feeds local textile mills and traditional weaving industries. Unlike the commercial hub of Lagos, North Central Nigeria is characterised by a blend of deep-rooted indigenous textile traditions and the burgeoning political and administrative market of Abuja (Owoloyi et al., 2024).

The Tiv people of Benue State and the Ebira-Tao people of Kogi State maintain vibrant cottage industries centred on hand-woven fabrics like Anger and Agbende-a-Kurugh, where women are dominant producers (Iorja, 2018). Also, cities like Jos in Plateau State host resilient communities of female roadside vendors and fashion cooperatives that thrive despite infrastructural deficits. The region's unique mix of agrarian raw material availability, cultural heritage, and proximity to the administrative capital makes it a distinct environment for examining the interplay between fashion MSMEs and women's socio-economic outcomes.

Despite the visible participation of women in the fashion sector, there remains a critical disconnect in the academic literature regarding their specific socio-economic outcomes in this geopolitical zone. Existing studies have largely focused on the challenges of female entrepreneurship in general or have concentrated heavily on the commercial hubs of Lagos and the South-West (Obonyilo et al., 2024; Abdulraheem et al., 2024).

While research acknowledges the cultural value of textiles in places like Kogi and Benue, there is a paucity of research that holistically examines the entire value chain from fibre to retail through a gendered economic lens. Also, existing studies have not sufficiently disaggregated the specific contributions of the different segments of the fashion and apparel value chain to women's household welfare in North Central Nigeria. Furthermore, tailored or specific strategies that can promote socio-economic wellbeing for women engaged in the fashion and apparel value chain MSMEs in the North Central region remain under-researched.

This study aims to fill this gap by providing a granular understanding and empirical evidence on how activities of women-specific fashion MSMEs in North Central Nigeria translate into measurable socioeconomic outcomes for women. Also, stating the hypothesis that fashion/apparel MSMEs do not significantly promote the socioeconomic wellbeing of women in north central Nigeria represents a null position that challenges the assumed positive socioeconomic outcomes of these enterprises on women of north central Nigeria.

Regionally, the study aims to create economic viability for indigenous textile hubs that are often overshadowed by the national focus on oil and general commerce and suggest tailored solutions that will enhance the socioeconomic well-being of women participating in fashion/apparel MSMEs in the region.

Statement of the Problem

Despite constituting 96.9% of businesses and contributing 46.3% to Nigeria's GDP, the MSME sector is characterised by a stark gender disparity in formalisation and growth potential. As revealed by Nwonye (2024), women account for 41% of micro-business ownership in Nigeria, yet they are disproportionately concentrated in the informal sector, with only 13.57% representation in the formal business sector compared to 86.43% for men.

Structural constraints remain pervasive; Nigeria ranks 123rd out of 146 countries on the global gender gap index, highlighting severe deficits in women's access to financial and business development services. Consequently, approximately 80% of women-owned enterprises are forced to rely on personal savings for capitalisation due to systemic exclusion from formal credit markets. For Okesina (2021), this lack of financial integration forces women into a cycle of "survivalist" entrepreneurship rather than high-growth enterprise, limiting their contribution to national economic development.

Within the MSME landscape, the fashion and apparel sector, traditionally a female stronghold, is plagued by fragmentation, undervaluation, and infrastructural decay. Women entrepreneurs in this sector, particularly those in "simple textile" and tailoring ventures, are frequently under-represented and unable to exploit professional opportunities due to weak business orientation and difficulties securing property rights (Obonyilo, 2024). The operational environment is hostile; fashion MSMEs are severely hampered by an epileptic power supply, which necessitates the use of expensive generators, thereby driving up production costs and eroding competitiveness against imported alternatives (Matala et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the sector is struggling with the influx of second-hand clothing and a lack of standardisation, which diminishes the market share of indigenous producers (Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria [SMEDAN], 2022). A critical limitation in current literature and policy is the tendency to treat women's fashion enterprises as a homogeneous group, ignoring the distinct economic realities across the value chain. Existing studies often analyse "fashion designers" or "traditional weavers" (Iorja, 2018) in isolation,

failing to interrogate the connectivity or lack thereof between raw material sourcing, production, and retail.

There is a lack of evidence regarding how value is added or lost at each stage for women-owned firms. For instance, while some women engage in weaving as a cultural heritage, others operate in high-competition retail environments; yet, research revealed by Hassan (2021) rarely disaggregates how these differing roles specifically impact business expansion and profitability.

The literature notes that women often struggle to enter new segments of the fashion business due to resource unavailability, but the specific value-chain bottlenecks preventing this transition remain underexplored.

Empirical studies on women's entrepreneurship in Nigeria exhibit a significant geographical bias, with a preponderance of research focused on the commercial hubs of Lagos and the South-West, or the insurgency-impacted North-East. North Central Nigeria is conspicuously under-represented in the literature, despite its unique status as a "Central Zone" for cotton production and its rich heritage of indigenous textile industries, such as the Tiv and Ebira weaving traditions. The specific socio-economic dynamics of the North Central region, where cultural conservatism intersects with the proximity to the Federal Capital Territory, create a unique set of challenges and opportunities that generalised Nigerian studies fail to capture.

Finally, there is a paucity of evidence linking specific fashion MSME activities to tangible socio-economic outcomes for women in this region. While general literature asserts that women's entrepreneurship reduces poverty, there is conflicting evidence regarding whether micro-credits and business profits in this sector are actually reinvested for business growth or diverted to household consumption and social provision due to the state's failure to provide basic welfare. Research has largely omitted the specific drivers of savings behaviour and financial resilience among these women. Consequently, it remains unclear whether participation in the fashion and apparel MSMEs in North Central Nigeria serves as a genuine vehicle for economic transformation or merely a subsistence mechanism for women absorbing economic shocks.

This study, therefore, seeks to examine the role of women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs in promoting the socio-economic well-being of women in North Central Nigeria. The paper specifically identifies the various types of women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs in North Central Nigeria and suggests the various strategies that can enhance the socio-economic well-being of women engaged in fashion and apparel MSMEs in North Central Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What are the women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs in North Central Nigeria?
2. In what ways do women-specific fashion/apparel MSMEs contribute to promoting their socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria?
3. What strategies can promote the socio-economic well-being of women in MSMEs in North Central Nigeria?

The objectives of this paper include:

1. Identify the various types of women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs in North Central Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the various dimensions of fashion and apparel MSMEs use in promoting the socio-economic well-being of women in North Central Nigeria.
3. To suggest the various strategies that can enhance the socioeconomic wellbeing of women engaged in fashion and apparel value MSMEs in North Central Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis formulated for testing in this study is:

i. H_{0ii}: Fashion/apparel MSMEs do not significantly promote socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Clarification

Women-Specific Fashion and Apparel MSMEs

Women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs are micro, small and medium enterprises owned, managed, or predominantly operated by women within the fashion value chain, including tailoring, garment production, fashion design, retailing, and accessories. While this definition appears operational, the literature increasingly moves beyond size and ownership criteria to conceptualise women-owned MSMEs as gendered economic formations embedded in social relations that structure women's access to productive resources (Ogundana et al., 2021).

From a sociological perspective, we cannot merely understand these enterprises as economic units responding to market signals. Rather, they are shaped by historically constituted gender hierarchies that regulate women's access to capital, mobility, education, and networks. Women's over-representation in fashion and apparel MSMEs is not accidental; it reflects a broader sexual division of labour in which "feminised" skills such as sewing, design, and aesthetic labour are socially constructed as extensions of domestic work. This framing helps explain why women's enterprises are often undervalued, informalised, and excluded from high-return segments of the market, despite their economic and cultural significance.

In Nigeria, fashion and apparel MSMEs are particularly feminised due to their relatively low entry barriers, home-based possibilities, and compatibility with women's domestic responsibilities (Modibbo, 2025). However, these same characteristics that facilitate entry also reproduce structural vulnerability. Home-based production, while enabling flexibility, often limits scale, visibility, and bargaining power, reinforcing women's marginal positioning within the broader economy. Consequently, women-specific fashion MSMEs function simultaneously as income-generating ventures and as adaptive survival strategies within labour markets that systematically disadvantage women through unemployment, underemployment, and occupational segregation.

Understanding the socioeconomic effects of women-specific fashion MSMEs, therefore, requires an explicit, gender-sensitive analytical lens that recognises both agency and constraint. Women exercise entrepreneurial agency by creating livelihoods within restrictive environments, but social norms, household expectations, and institutional exclusions condition their choices. This duality underscores the importance of analysing women's MSMEs not only in terms of performance outcomes but also in relation to the gendered structures that shape those outcomes.

Fashion and Apparel Value Chain

The fashion and apparel value chain comprises interconnected activities ranging from design and production (tailoring, garment making, creative design) to distribution, retail, and accessories. Value-chain scholarship emphasises that economic value is not evenly distributed across these activities; rather, chains are characterised by hierarchies of value capture, where certain nodes command higher returns due to skill intensity, control over branding, and access to markets (Strydom & Kempen, 2021).

In developing-country contexts, women are disproportionately concentrated in lower-value or informal segments of the chain, particularly small-scale tailoring and retail activities (Ogundana et al., 2021; Abdulraheem et al., 2024). This concentration is often interpreted as a

function of individual limitations, such as a lack of capital or education. However, a structural reading suggests that women's positioning reflects systemic exclusion from higher-value segments, including formal manufacturing, large-scale distribution, and export-orientated production, which are typically capital-intensive and male-dominated.

Treating fashion MSMEs as a single category, therefore, obscures critical intra-sectoral differences. It collapses heterogeneous activities into a uniform analytical unit, masking how women's location within the value chain shapes not only income levels but also exposure to risk, opportunities for learning, and prospects for upgrading. A value-chain approach allows for a more precise assessment of how participation in design and production may enable skill accumulation and creative autonomy, whereas engagement in retail and accessories may prioritise accessibility and survival over long-term growth. Importantly, this perspective shifts the analytical focus from whether women participate in fashion MSMEs to where they participate and under what conditions. Such differentiation is essential for understanding the uneven socio-economic outcomes observed among women entrepreneurs and for designing interventions that move beyond generic MSME support toward segment-specific strategies.

Socio-Economic Outcomes of Women Entrepreneurs

Socio-economic outcomes in women's entrepreneurial literature are increasingly conceptualised as multidimensional, encompassing income generation, employment creation, empowerment, human capital development, and wellbeing. While income remains a central indicator, feminist and development scholars argue that economic gains alone do not fully capture women's advancement, particularly in contexts where gender norms constrain women's control over income and limit their decision-making power within households and communities (Raspati & Kadiyono, 2023).

This critique is especially relevant in patriarchal settings where women's earnings may be appropriated or where increased income does not translate into enhanced autonomy. As such, socio-economic outcomes must be understood in terms of both material improvements and shifts in power relations. In this framing, empowerment is not simply an outcome but a process, reflected in women's ability to make strategic life choices, invest in their businesses, and negotiate social expectations. In the context of fashion MSMEs, socio-economic outcomes extend beyond financial returns to include skill acquisition, social recognition, and reduced vulnerability to poverty (Okolie et al., 2021; Maimuna et al., 2022).

Skill development through tailoring, design, and apprenticeships enhances women's human capital, while social visibility as entrepreneurs can challenge normative assumptions about women's economic roles. However, these outcomes are uneven and contingent on market access, institutional support, and household dynamics. This multidimensional framing underpins the present study's assessment of women's outcomes beyond purely financial performance. By examining income, empowerment, and well-being simultaneously, the study acknowledges that women's entrepreneurship in fashion and apparel MSMEs produces complex and sometimes contradictory effects, reinforcing the need for empirically grounded, context-specific analysis.

Across global development literature, women-owned MSMEs are consistently positioned as central to income generation, employment creation, and poverty reduction, particularly within labour-intensive sectors such as apparel and garments (Strydom & Kempen, 2021). Fashion-related enterprises occupy a distinctive place in this scholarship because they combine relatively low barriers to entry with strong potential for skill transmission through informal apprenticeships and on-the-job learning. In many developing economies, tailoring and garment-making function not only as income-generating activities but also as informal training systems through which women acquire technical, managerial, and creative competencies.

Yet global evidence also reveals a persistent tension between accessibility and vulnerability. While the fashion sector offers women entry into entrepreneurship, it simultaneously exposes them to unstable demand, price competition, and limited bargaining power within broader market structures. Studies repeatedly point to restricted access to finance and weak integration into formal value chains as factors that constrain women's ability to scale their enterprises or move into higher-value activities. These vulnerabilities suggest that participation alone does not guarantee sustained socio-economic advancement.

A critical limitation of the global literature lies in its tendency to treat fashion and apparel MSMEs as a monolithic sector. Much of the evidence aggregates garments, textiles, and apparel manufacturing without disaggregating the distinct activities that constitute the value chain. As a result, little is known about how socio-economic returns differ between women engaged in design-intensive production, routine tailoring, retail, or accessories. This lack of differentiation obscures the uneven ways in which value is created and captured within the fashion economy, limiting the explanatory power of global findings for policy and practice.

Within African contexts, women-owned MSMEs are widely understood as critical mechanisms for both economic survival and social reproduction, particularly in settings characterised by limited formal employment opportunities. Apparel-related enterprises, such as tailoring, garment production, fabric trading, and accessories, feature prominently in this literature due to their cultural embeddedness and accessibility to women across urban and rural spaces (Modibbo, 2025). Empirical studies consistently associate these activities with income stability, household support, and local employment generation.

However, African scholarship has tended to frame women's entrepreneurship predominantly through a constrained lens, foregrounding barriers such as limited access to finance, low educational attainment, and restrictive socio-cultural norms (Halkias et al., 2011). While this focus has been important in documenting structural inequalities, it has also narrowed analytical attention toward what women lack, rather than how women actively navigate and reshape economic spaces within existing constraints. Consequently, the socio-economic effects of women's enterprises are often inferred rather than empirically examined.

Moreover, the dominance of constraint-focused analyses has meant that fewer studies interrogate the mechanisms through which fashion and apparel MSMEs generate empowerment and well-being. Questions regarding how different activities within the fashion value chain shape income stability, skill accumulation, and social status remain insufficiently explored. This gap is particularly significant given the heterogeneity of African fashion economies, where informal production, social networks, and cultural aesthetics play a central role in shaping enterprise outcomes. In Nigeria, empirical research affirms the importance of women-owned MSMEs as engines of employment creation and poverty reduction, with women-led firms often exhibiting notable survival rates and employment-generating capacity (Saibu et al., 2024). Within the fashion and apparel sectors, tailoring, fashion design, and accessories have been identified as key livelihood strategies for women, especially in urban and peri-urban contexts where demand for customised clothing and fashion services remains high (Abdulraheem et al., 2024; Modibbo, 2025).

Beyond income generation, Nigerian studies increasingly highlight the relationship between women's participation in MSMEs and broader empowerment outcomes. Engagement in fashion enterprises has been linked to enhanced self-reliance, increased decision-making autonomy, and improved social recognition, particularly when women possess business skills and educational capital (Ogundana et al., 2021; Raspati & Kadiyono, 2023). More recent evidence from North Central Nigeria underscores the role of financial inclusion in strengthening women's human capital, suggesting that access to credit and advisory services enables women to invest in skills development and enterprise upgrading (Mohammed-Adimoha et al., 2025).

Despite these insights, Nigerian scholarship remains limited in two important respects. First, women-owned MSMEs are frequently treated as a homogeneous category, with little attention to differences across sectors or value-chain positions. Second, empirical studies are geographically concentrated in southern regions, particularly the southwest, where fashion industries are more visible and formalised. This regional bias has left North Central Nigeria relatively under-researched, despite its distinct socio-economic conditions and the prevalence of women-owned fashion MSMEs operating under different cultural and market dynamics. Taken together, these limitations point to the need for research that disaggregates women's fashion enterprises along value-chain lines and situates analysis within specific regional contexts. Addressing this gap is essential for understanding not only whether women-owned fashion SMEs contribute to socio-economic outcomes but also how and under what conditions such contributions are realised.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts empowerment theory and intersectional theory. The theory of empowerment emerges from social work and community psychology and is associated with social scientist Julian Rappaport (1981). It was further developed and popularised by Zimmerman (1995, 2000). The theory was later modified by Sazama and Young (2006) and Reischl, Zimmerman, Morrel-Samuels, Franzen, Faulk, Eisman, and Roberts (2011). The basic tenet of empowerment theory is fostering autonomy and self-determination; the theory believes that everyone has the potential to gain control over their lives and the world, and the theory sees working with others to achieve a common goal as a key principle to empowerment. Women Empowerment Theory provides the foundation for analysing how engagement with fashion MSMEs enhances women's access to resources, decision-making power, and wellbeing (Ogundana et al., 2021). The theory argues that when women gain access to productive resources and income-generating opportunities, their bargaining power, autonomy, and overall well-being improve. In the context of women's entrepreneurship, empowerment is not limited to income acquisition; it involves structural transformation in gender relations. Women's access to business ownership and management strengthens their capacity to influence household and community-level decisions. This theory will help women who are engaged in women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs (clothing design, garment production, textile finishing, accessories production, and retail enterprises) to have independent streams of income and productive assets. In North Central Nigeria, where women often face limited formal employment opportunities and restricted access to financial capital, fashion and apparel MSMEs offer relatively accessible pathways to economic participation.

Economic empowerment derived from fashion and apparel MSMEs contributes directly to socio-economic well-being by improving income stability, household well-being, and livelihood security. Beyond economic gains, fashion and apparel entrepreneurship fosters social and psychological empowerment. Women entrepreneurs often build networks through trade associations and market interactions, increasing their social capital and community recognition. The confidence gained from managing enterprises strengthens their entrepreneurial identity and self-efficacy, which are essential components of sustained empowerment. Empowerment theory maintains that women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs function as vehicles for enhancing women's socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria. This means that women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs serve as mechanisms through which empowerment translates into measurable socio-economic outcomes, and the empowerment theory is a suitable lens for this study.

Intersectionality theory

The proponent of intersectionality theory is Kimberly Williams Crenshaw (1989), a law professor and social theorist who introduced the term ‘intersectionality’ in the context of a discussion of Black women’s employment in the USA (Yuval-Davis, 2006:193). The intersectional theory acknowledges the intersectionality of gender, race, class, and other social identities in shaping women’s experiences as entrepreneurs. It argued that understanding and addressing the unique challenges faced by women from diverse backgrounds is crucial for promoting sustainable entrepreneurship.

The theory enriches the analysis by recognising that women entrepreneurs’ experiences are shaped by intersecting factors such as gender norms, household roles, education, market access, and regional context. This perspective is particularly relevant in North Central Nigeria, where socio-cultural expectations and institutional constraints significantly influence women’s entrepreneurial outcomes (Modibbo, 2025; Otaokpukpu & Nwankwo, 2024).

Together, these frameworks enable a nuanced understanding of how and why women-specific fashion MSMEs contribute to socio-economic outcomes under varying cultures and identities and market and policy conditions.

METHODOLOGY

The paper employs a descriptive survey design, using both the quantitative and qualitative methods of inquiry. The population of 912,327 adult women in the three selected states of North Central Nigeria, according to the National Bureau of Statistics (2023), was used to draw the sample frame for the study using Taro's (1967) sample size determination formula. The sample size for this study is 1,111 women sampled from the three selected states (Benue, Nasarawa, and Abuja) of North Central Nigeria. Quantitative data were gathered through structured questionnaires; 1,111 copies of questionnaires were administered, and 1,044 copies (94%) were duly completed and used for analysis. Qualitative data were collected through key informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs). Nine key informant interviews and six FGD sessions were carried out in the three states purposely selected for the study; the selection is based on two complementary reasons: geographical diversity and socio-economic indicators. A proportional sampling technique was used to share the sample size among the states. In the second stage, a simple random sampling technique was adopted to select LGAs for the study. The choice of the selection was to give an equal chance without being biased. Two LGAs will be selected across each selected state, making a total of 6 LGAs. (For Abuja-FCT, Abuja Municipal Area Council and Bwari will be selected; for Nasarawa State, Lafia and Doma; and for Benue State, Makurdi and Obi). Also, a simple random sampling technique was used to select two (2) political wards from each selected LGA, making a total of 12 wards for the study. Quantitative data was analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version, while qualitative data was transcribed and analysed using the OpenAI Whisper model, implemented through Python scripts in Google Colab. This automated transcription approach ensured high accuracy and efficiency, particularly in capturing multilingual exchanges and varied speech patterns across participants. The transcripts were then carefully reviewed, translated, and back-translated to ensure linguistic and contextual accuracy. The final verified texts were word-processed and prepared for systematic content and thematic analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of women participating in fashion and apparel (MSMEs) and the potential influence on their socio-economic well-being. The age distribution showed that the majority of respondents fell within the economically active age brackets of 25 to 44 years (60%), with a mean age of 39.9 years and a standard deviation of

16.1. This implies that most participants are in their productive years, which is crucial for enterprise development and sustainability. Also, the large standard deviation ($SD > 2$) indicates a wide spread in terms of the age of respondents, implying that all categories of age groups were captured in the study. Respondents aged 18–24 represent a relatively small share (11%), which may reflect the greater participation of older women in MSMEs, particularly those with family obligations. Marital status revealed that a significant majority of respondents were married (55.1%), while 25.6% were single, and the rest were either separated, widowed, or divorced. This highlights that marital responsibilities shape women’s entrepreneurial activities, either by providing household support for business sustainability or by increasing financial pressures that drive them into MSMEs for livelihood security. Also, in terms of education, the majority of respondents have either primary (41.8%) or secondary education (22.3%), while only 17.5% have attained tertiary education and 18.4% have no formal education. This points to the fact that a large portion of women entrepreneurs operate with limited formal education, which could affect their managerial capacity, financial literacy, and ability to scale businesses. Occupational distribution showed that trading dominates (52.5%), followed by farming (22.9%) and self-employment (16.8%). Civil servants represent only 5.4%, which lends support to the view that women predominantly engage in informal economic activities. This concentration in trading and farming implies that women’s enterprises are mostly small-scale and survival-driven, pointing to their vulnerability to market fluctuations and limited access to formal financing. Furthermore, religious affiliation showed that Christianity (65.6%) and Islam (25.8%) are the dominant faiths, while traditional and other religions constitute smaller percentages. These affiliations may influence women’s access to business networks, credit associations, and cooperative support systems, which are often structured along religious lines. The place of residence is evenly split between rural (50.1%) and urban (49.9%) areas. This finding suggests that MSMEs constitute a critical component of economic activity in both rural and urban settings, with rural women possibly facing greater infrastructural and market access challenges compared to their urban counterparts. Income levels showed that most respondents earn above ₦50,000 monthly, with 35% earning between ₦50,001 and ₦70,000 and 37.4% earning ₦70,001 and above. Only 2% earn less than ₦10,000. This distribution suggests that engagement in MSMEs contributes significantly to improving women’s income and socio-economic well-being. However, income disparities also point to uneven benefits, possibly influenced by enterprise type, scale of operations, or access to resources.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Attributes of Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Std.
Age			39.9	16.1
18-24	115	11.0		
25-34	292	28.0		
35-44	334	32.0		
45-54	222	21.3		
55 and above:	81	7.8		
Marital Status				
Single	267	25.6		
Married	575	55.1		
Separated	70	6.7		
Widowed	80	7.7		
Divorced	52	5.0		
Level of Education				
Non-formal education	192	18.4		
Primary	436	41.8		
Secondary	233	22.3		
Tertiary	183	17.5		
Occupation				
Trading	548	52.5		

Civil Service	56	5.4
Self-employed	175	16.8
Farming	239	22.9
Others	26	2.5
Religion		
Christianity	685	65.6
Islam	269	25.8
Africa Religion	47	4.5
Others	43	4.1
Place of Residence		
Rural	523	50.1
Urban	521	49.9
Income Level		
Less than 10,000	21	2.0
10,001-30,000	78	7.5
30,001-50,000	189	18.1
50,001-70,000	366	35.0
70,001 and above	390	37.4

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2: Distribution of responses by knowledge about Fashion and apparel MSMEs

Question	Yes	No	Not sure
1. Do you own a fashion and apparel MSME?	730 (69.9%)	261 (25.0%)	53 (5.1%)
0. Do you think Fashion and apparel (MSMEs) have contributed to the socioeconomic well-being of women in North Central Nigeria	412 (56.4%)	222 (30.4%)	96 (13.2%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 2 showed the distribution of responses on knowledge about fashion and apparel MSMEs, providing insight into women's level of participation and perception of their impact on socio-economic well-being. The data revealed that a significant percentage of the respondents (69.9%) own MSMEs, while 25% do not, and 5.1% were unsure. This finding signifies that a large majority of women are directly engaged in entrepreneurial activities.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents by what constitutes Socio-economic well-being

Category:	Socio-economics Activities	Frequency	%
High Socio-economic well-being	Interaction with people	192	18.6
	Increased access to funding	141	13.5
	Reduced social exclusion	138	13.2
	More access to happiness	123	11.8
Average Socio-economic well-being	Being gainfully employed	110	10.5
	Improve income	106	10.2
	Self-improvement	98	9.4
Low Socio-economic well-being	Meeting basic needs	74	7.1

Increased happiness	32	3.1
Freedom of choices	28	2.6
Total	1,044	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

In table 3, respondents in the study had diverse views of what constitutes socio-economic well-being. These activities were categorised into high, average, and low socio-economic well-being, as captured in Table 3. As shown in the table above, 57.1% of the respondents categorised diverse situations as high socio-economic well-being. Accordingly, interaction with people (18.6%), increased access to funding (13.5%), reduced social exclusion (13.2%) and more access to happiness (11.8%) were categorised as high socio-economic well-being by the respondents. Similarly, situations considered as average socio-economic well-being include being gainfully employed (10.5%), improved income (10.2%) and self-improvement (9.4%). Accordingly, 30.1% of the respondents believed that people who found themselves in the above situation were categorised as people with average socio-economic well-being in the study location. The respondents believed that residents who have the capability of meeting basic needs (7.1%), increased their happiness (3.1%) and have freedom of choices (2.6%) were categorised as people with low socio-economic well-being in the study location. The implication of these statistics is that respondents have diverse opinions on what constitutes socio-economic well-being in the study area.

Fashion/Apparel Enterprises and Socioeconomic Well-being of Women

Table 4. Distribution of responses on fashion and apparel enterprises and socioeconomic well-being of women

Do you think women-led fashion/apparel MSMEs contribute to?	Yes	No	Not sure
Creating job opportunities	491 (67.3%)	188 (25.8%)	51 (7.0%)
Income generation	512 (70.1%)	178 (24.4%)	40 (5.5%)
Development of valuable skills	475 (65.1%)	192 (26.3%)	63 (8.6%)
Promoting leadership skills	491 (67.3%)	173 (23.7%)	66 (9.0%)
Increasing access to funding	505 (69.2%)	159 (21.8%)	6 (9.0%)
Poverty reduction	502 (68.8%)	184 (25.2%)	44 (6.0%)
Self-improvement through training/internship.	517 (70.8%)	160 (21.9%)	53 (7.3%)
Providing avenues for new business ideas	499 (68.4%)	149 (20.4%)	82 (11.2%)
Increasing networking opportunities/professional relationships	514 (70.4%)	148 (20.3%)	68 (9.3%)
Inspiring women and girls in entrepreneurial potential	476 (65.2%)	180 (24.7%)	74 (10.1%)

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

The responses on fashion and apparel enterprises highlighted the important role that women-led MSMEs play in advancing socio-economic well-being. A majority of the respondents affirmed that these enterprises contribute positively across different dimensions.

Most notably, 70.8% agreed that fashion and apparel MSMEs enhance self-improvement through training and internships, while 70.4% recognised their role in increasing networking opportunities and professional relationships. This suggests that beyond financial benefits, women in the fashion sector gain personal development, mentorship opportunities, and stronger social capital, all of which are essential for entrepreneurial growth. The implication is that fashion enterprises serve as platforms for capacity building, collaboration, and long-term career advancement for women.

Income generation (70.1%), access to funding (69.2%), poverty reduction (68.8%), and creation of job opportunities (67.3%) also ranked high. This reflects the significant economic benefits of fashion-related enterprises, demonstrating their capacity to improve household incomes, provide employment, and uplift communities. The implication is that fashion MSMEs are not only survivalist ventures but also drivers of economic empowerment and poverty alleviation. Targeted financial support, access to credit, and market expansion could further enhance these economic contributions.

Skill development and leadership promotion were also strongly recognised, with 65.1% and 67.3%, respectively, affirming that fashion enterprises provide valuable skills and nurture leadership among women. This shows that fashion MSMEs act as training grounds where women gain technical, managerial, and leadership abilities. The implication is that engagement in fashion enterprises boosts women’s confidence and strengthens their capacity to take on leadership roles both in business and society. Lastly, other contributions include providing avenues for new business ideas (68.4%) and inspiring women and girls in entrepreneurial potential (65.2%). This reflects the innovative and motivational aspects of fashion and apparel MSMEs, which not only encourage creativity but also act as role models for younger women. The implication is that fashion enterprises help sustain a cycle of entrepreneurship by inspiring new generations of women to participate in business, thereby expanding women’s role in economic development.

Hypothesis

H₀: Fashion/Apparel MSMEs do not significantly promote socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria

H₁: Fashion/Apparel MSMEs significantly promote socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria

Table 5: Linear regression analysis on Fashion/Apparel MSMEs and socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R	Std. Error			
1	.864a	.746	.743	.392			
2	Sources of variance		Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
	Regression	324.538	10	32.454	211.424	.000 ^b	
	Residual	110.367	719	.154			
	Total	434.905	729				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	

Independent Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.084	.047		-1.772	.077
Creating job opportunities	-.060	.035	-.048	-1.728	.084
Income generation	.405	.034	.305	11.883	.000
Development of valuable skills	.466	.051	.391	9.141	.000
Promoting leadership skills	-.171	.118	-.144	-1.449	.148
Increasing access to funding	.148	.120	.124	1.235	.217
Poverty reduction	.279	.032	.215	8.654	.000
Self-improvement through training / internship.	.008	.043	.006	.188	.851
Proving avenues for new business ideas	.061	.040	.054	1.543	.123
Increasing networking opportunities/professional relationships	.104	.048	.088	2.190	.029
Inspiring women and girls in entrepreneurial potential	.128	.040	.112	3.239	.001

The regression results in Table 5 revealed a strong positive relationship between fashion/apparel MSMEs and socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria, with an R value of .864 and an R² of .746, indicating that 74.6% of the variation in socio-economic well-being is explained by the independent variables. The F-statistic ($F = 211.424$, $p = .000$) confirms the model's overall statistical significance. Significant predictors include income generation ($\beta = .305$, $p < .001$), development of valuable skills ($\beta = .391$, $p < .001$), poverty reduction ($\beta = .215$, $p < .001$), increasing networking opportunities/professional relationships ($\beta = .088$, $p = .029$), and inspiring women and girls in entrepreneurial potential ($\beta = .112$, $p = .001$). Other variables, such as creating job opportunities ($p = .084$), promoting leadership skills ($p = .148$), increasing access to funding ($p = .217$), self-improvement through training/internship ($p = .851$), and providing avenues for new business ideas ($p = .123$), do not show significant contributions.

Given that the model's p-value (.000) is below 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. This indicates that fashion/apparel MSMEs significantly promote socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria. The quantitative data is buttressed by findings from the qualitative study: A participant during the KII asserted the following:

I will say here that my fashion business has really helped me a lot. I sew for myself. I don't pay for anybody to sew for me; I always look good, and this gives my husband great joy. I sew for my children too. The income that comes from my business has increased my investment. I pay school fees for my younger ones, and I fix up little things in the house without waiting for my husband. (Fashion designer, Kwandere, Nasarawa State)

Complementing the above, a participant in the focus group discussion maintained the following:

I sell sample material, fairly used clothes and other tailoring accessories, and this has helped a lot of women who dwell in North Central... . To reduce the cost of travelling far to get these materials, these sample materials and fairly used clothes are cheap. This has helped particularly women because they are our main customers. Many women have more fashionable clothes to meet any occasion they want to attend, and this has boosted their wellbeing (Bose boutique, Nyanya, Abuja)

Evidence from KII also revealed how fashion and apparel SMSEs can bring about financial benefits, personal confidence and pride. A participant during the focus group posits the following:

I sell ladies' wares and am also a makeup artist. What we do in this enterprise helps women a lot personally. I am happy because I don't have to run to anybody for help; I'd rather cash out... We take care of women's outfits and outlooks. Our enterprise helps women to always look good, especially during weddings and traditional marriages, and their husbands appreciate their looks a lot. This business is very good. I thank God (ladies' wear marketer/Makeup artist, Bwari, Abuja)

Participants also recounted the resourcefulness required to start and develop skills in the fashion/apparel business. They emphasised the importance of saving from modest earnings and hands-on learning, often utilising readily available materials.

A key informant interviewer posited that

My fashion business is excelling; saving is very important here. You need to save from the little you have... It's all about savings. You save income to be able to purchase that machine as well as the materials you need before you think of any grant. I have to cultivate the habit of saving so as to invest; otherwise, this business will not work. (Mrs C, Fashion Designer, Garki ward, Abuja)

Complementing the above, another focus group discussant maintained that:

I learnt to save money. This has helped me over the years to buy more materials. There are those who have been in the tailoring business; I usually ask them for pieces of clothes they may not be using again and then use them to continue to learn or practise, and then later I started buying some little cheap material to sew for myself and my children. Before I realised it, I had perfected it. Personally, I also watch YouTube videos. And my business is growing.” (Mrs C, Fashion Designer, Doka, Nasarawa State)

Personal promotion is a key approach, where participants literally become their own advertisements, showcasing their work through what they and their children wear.

A confirmation from a key informant revealed the following:

I usually order materials. I sew for myself and the children as a strategy; this advertises my business a lot. I also post both the materials and sewn outfits through social media that are already branded 'made by me'. From there, I advertise my products; some women order the materials from my shop, and we still sew for them. I have about nine staff working with me. It has been nice. (Female Dressmaker Nyanya, Abuja)

Personal promotion and modern digital platforms, particularly WhatsApp and Facebook, serve as crucial tools for broader reach, allowing entrepreneurs to display their creations and apparel to a wider audience. Despite these varied efforts, respondents maintained that the market response can often be gradual.

Despite these successes, the qualitative data also revealed the high cost of materials and a fluctuating market as factors affecting business turnover. A participant during the focus group discussion maintained the following:

My enterprise is so affected as a result of the problem of inflation, the high cost of goods in the market... you will find out that you will buy a material today... You sold it, and when you want to go and buy the material again to sew another one, the price has changed. This is terrible; this reduces the income you've already had. (Female, Fashion Designer/Farmer)

The participants pleaded that the authorities concerned should, as a matter of urgency, address the issue of inflation to save female-led MSMEs in the region.

The study found that women-led fashion and apparel enterprises play a significant role in enhancing the socioeconomic well-being of women. Many respondents agreed that such enterprises create job opportunities, generate income, and contribute to poverty reduction. This finding aligned with Adebayo and Ayeni (2021), who argued that fashion enterprises empower women by providing employment and income, thereby reducing poverty in local communities. Similarly, Ogundele and Olajide (2020) contended that the fashion and apparel sector is a critical avenue through which women entrepreneurs contribute to both household and community welfare by ensuring financial independence. The evidence also supports the view of Ojo and Akinlabi (2022), who maintain that women-led MSMEs are instrumental in poverty alleviation and skill acquisition across Nigeria.

The findings also indicated that fashion enterprises are not limited to income generation but also play a major role in developing valuable and leadership skills among women. This agrees with the submission of Eze and Nwachukwu (2021), who observed that fashion entrepreneurship serves as a training ground for women to acquire not only vocational but also managerial and leadership skills. Similarly, Oladipo and Lawal (2023) highlighted that women in the apparel industry are often positioned as role models within their communities, inspiring other women and girls to pursue entrepreneurial endeavours. These outcomes demonstrate that women-led enterprises extend their benefits beyond economics, touching on empowerment and personal development.

Moreover, the findings showed that women-led fashion enterprises increase access to funding and provide platforms for new business ideas and networking. This is consistent with the position of Ojo (2020), who asserted that fashion businesses create social and financial capital that enables women to gain easier access to credit facilities and expand their entrepreneurial initiatives. In the same vein, Adeola and Yusuf (2022) argued that such enterprises foster business partnerships and professional networking, which are vital for growth and sustainability in competitive markets. Furthermore, the inspirational role of these enterprises for women and girls resonates with the findings of Abiola and Adeyemi (2021), who emphasised that entrepreneurial visibility among women motivates younger generations to recognise entrepreneurship as a viable career path.

However, a contrary view exists. Some respondents disagreed that fashion and apparel enterprises significantly improve socioeconomic wellbeing. This aligns with the argument of Ibrahim and Musa (2020), who note that many women-led enterprises in Nigeria are hindered by structural barriers such as inadequate capital, lack of government support, and poor access to international markets, which limit their socioeconomic impact. Similarly, Okafor and Chukwu (2022) argued that the informal nature of most fashion MSMEs often leads to unstable incomes and poor scalability, thereby limiting their contribution to long-term economic empowerment. These criticisms highlight that while women-led fashion enterprises have great potential to improve the socioeconomic development of women, structural challenges constrain their full impact.

CONCLUSIONS

Drawing on the evidence, analysed through both quantitative and qualitative methods, this study reaches the following conclusions regarding the role of women-led fashion and apparel MSMEs in North Central Nigeria:

1. Women-led fashion and apparel MSMEs are a central force in advancing socio-economic development in the North Central Region. Most of the respondents agreed that fashion and apparel MSMEs have enhanced their social, economic, and psychological empowerment as well as household bargaining power.

2. The significance of their participation in these enterprises not only raises their income levels but also strengthens social capital, fosters inclusion, and enhances women's sense of agency and well-being. This means that. Beyond economic returns, MSMEs create spaces for interaction and collective identity, which respondents consistently identified as integral to their quality of life.
3. Fashion and apparel MSMEs exhibit the strongest influence on women's well-being ($R^2=74.6\%$) because of their ability to provide a steady income, build transferable skills, and expand professional networks.
4. The study reveals that women who were involved in fashion/apparel MSMEs found happiness in what they were doing; their enterprises, apart from generating income for them to solve pertinent problems, created avenues for them to make new friends, promoting their general wellbeing.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings and conclusions of this study suggest the following measures for strengthening the role of women-specific fashion and apparel MSMEs in enhancing their socio-economic well-being in North Central Nigeria:

1. Women in the study area are aware of the role of fashion and apparel MSMEs in enhancing their socioeconomic wellbeing; government agencies at federal and state levels, in collaboration with development partners and women-focused organisations, should design and implement programmes for women in the fashion and apparel sector through vocational training, mentorship schemes, and awareness campaigns to encourage more women to be actively involved in fashion and apparel MSMEs.
2. Relevant financial institutions and government bodies should establish simplified, gender-responsive financing frameworks that enable women in fashion and apparel MSMEs to access loans and grants with minimal bureaucratic constraints. Also, evaluation and monitoring mechanisms should also be introduced to ensure transparency and equitable distribution of loans and grants.
3. Government at all levels should implement a harmonised and transparent tax system that eliminates multiple taxation; a more unified tax platform with clear tax guidelines should be adopted. Such tax reforms will help preserve working capital, encourage business expansion, and socio-economic wellbeing engaged in fashion and apparel enterprises

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